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Spiritualising Technology Naturalizing Religion and the Role of Self and Consciousness

The Only Wayout: A Critical Study

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of this paper is to understand the pragmatic approach from consciousness research and to explore the potential of human consciousness as preached by many enlightened soul, metaphysical poets, spiritual masters and other sapients to bring out the best of human intellect that can supersede that the challenges of Artificial Intelligence and modern days Frankenstein monster. The Artificial Intelligence is still considered one of the best technologies on this planet. However, the recent unpredicted developments in AI like ChatGPT, have really created a chaos and pell mell among academic intelligentsia and technocrats and also affected our society in serious way. It has also raised volley of questions including whether AI would be used for unethical purposes, or it will spoil the intelligence of supreme creation.

INTRODUCTION

Taking a general view of Artificial Intelligence, it is nothing but an organic development of innovative and extended human intelligence. Armed with science - technology and artificial intelligence the homosapience has overcome his biological limits with an intention to change laws of life and engineer inorganic beings. Envisaging a world where human intelligence ceases to exist. So, it is a moment where intelligence creates supreme inorganic beings or data processors and sidelined the living entities. In this present socio environment culture, we are totally possessed and obsessed with electronic gadgets and technology, sometimes it seems that we are subjugated and manipulated by the technology, delegated life and- death and all the decisions taken by non-human entity. Decision on our health, wealth and even all the work of our daily routine which once were taken by the doctors, wise persons, and experts of different field are now taken

digitally or other virtual platforms or influenced by algorithms. While AI based algorithms contribute immensely to human progress, their future prediction ushers a great threat as well. Now the fantasy no longer remains a fantasy as the age of human intelligence is on the verge of an end with advent of Dataism: the Data Religion.

Data Religion Versus Human Intelligence:

The data religion treats organisms as biological algorithms. According to scholars and historians Harari :--

Dataism thereby collapses the barrier between animals and machines. The Dataism takes looms large over the supreme creation of God as an existential threat seeking to replace human intelligence with artificial intelligence. When the world is shifted from human centric to data- centric, all data is processed, and all decisions are made by a single central processor. This Dystopian state as Harari terms, is none other than communalism. Though the onus of seeking a way out of this inevitable self-destruction mode of technology is on the shoulders of scientists, technocrats, and other motivational philanthropists to resolve this issue in the interest of mankind and to save world from possible destruction. Moreover, it is also important and relevant to know this deviation occurred. Philosophers have clearly understood the nature of mind from that of matter in order to give a new dimension on the basis of spirituality and religion.

The fundamental problem lies in the compartmentalisation of knowledge and perceiving human being as a mere bio-chemical being, apart from a spiritual being. When the evolution of artificial intelligence poses an imminent threat to the human intellect, a possible solution as per Hindu worldview is exploring the gradations of the higher consciousness. In the regard, in Sri Aurobindo, we find the integration of ancient Hindu wisdom and modern science, which together can be called Evolutionary Spirituality that combines 'philosophical brilliance and a profoundly enlightened consciousness'.

Suffering of the Mankind

At present mankind is undergoing an evolutionary crisis in which is concealed a choice of its destiny for a stage has been reached in which human mind has achieved in certain directions an enormous development while in others it stands arrested and bewildered and can no longer find its way. A structure of the external life has been raised up by man's ever-active mind and life-will a structure of an unmanageable hugeness and complexity for the service of his mental, vital, physical claims and urges, a complex political, social, administrative, economic, cultural machinery, an organized collective means for his intellectual, sensational, aesthetic and material satisfaction. Man has created a system of civilization which has become too big for his limited mental capacity and understanding and his still more

limited spiritual and moral capacity to utilize and manage, a too dangerous servant of his blundering ego and its Aurobindo.

Measures to Resolve the Issues Through Self Realisation & Inner Consciousness

To prevent the AI from taking over the control of human beings, a possible way out is to develop our human intelligence to the next level and explore the unlimited power of mind. It simply means elevating the human mind and intellect to higher levels and make it more powerful and wider than the machine intelligence. According to Sri Aurobindo, "Supermind is a plane of perfect knowledge, that has the full, integral truth of anything. It is a plane that man can rise to, above his current limited mentality, and have perfect understanding through revelations and power that is leaning down on the earth's consciousness. One can open to it, in order to transform the various aspects of one's being, as well as set right the conditions of life, creating sudden good fortune ("instantaneous miraculousness") for the person opening to it."

The many gradations of mind, which the modern science and the authors of dystopian non-fictions fail to see, are ranging from Higher Mind through Illumined Mind, Intuition, and Overmind up to Supermind, which is in between Sachchidananda- the one who is above all the manifestation and the flux of the many in the manifested universe. "We call itsupermind or the truth-consciousness, because it is a principle superior to mentality and exists, acts and proceeds in the fundamental truth and unity of things and not like the mind in their appearances and phenomenal divisions," Sri Aurobindo explains it in *The Life Divine*.

CONCLUSION

To conclude exploring the potential of human consciousness as experienced by many philosophers and fulfilling evolutionary intent and spiritual growth of life will bring out the best of the human intellect that can supersede the challenges of artificial intelligence and modern days fatal monster. This can be the only way to save the mankind in the days to come.

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